

Effect of Collaborative Improvisation on Creative-Thinking Fluency in Basic Science among Upper Basic Students in Makurdi, Benue State

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Abstract

Effect of Collaborative Improvisation on Creative-Thinking Fluency in Basic Science Among Upper Basic Students in Makurdi, Benue State was studied using pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group research design. The study was guided by two research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The study's population was made up of 1337 (680 male and 657 female) Upper Basic II government secondary school students in Makurdi metropolis. A multistage sample of 52 (22 male & 30 female) students in two intact classes from two schools was drawn. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and two-way ANCOVA. Findings showed no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation approach and those taught using Teacher Improvisation, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.001$; $p = .375 > .05$. Although; there existed a significant difference in creative-thinking fluency in favour of those taught using Collaborative Improvisation, $F_{(1, 45)} = 22.534$; $p = .000 < .05$, no significant difference existed in the students' creative-thinking fluency based on gender, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.291$; $p = .285 > .05$. Therefore, it was concluded that, enhancing creative-thinking fluency among students with different abilities can be achieved without any gender discrepancy by actively involving learners in the improvisation of instructional materials. Thus, Collaboration Improvisation Approach was recommended for teaching Basic Science in basic schools.

Keywords: Collaborative Improvisation (CI), Teacher Improvisation (TI), Creative-Thinking-Fluency, Mixed Ability and Gender

Introduction

In the midst of the fast-paced and ever-changing landscape of the current age, the imperative for individuals to harness their creative potential has never been more pronounced. Our world is marked by unprecedented technological advancements, global challenges, and dynamic economic shifts. In this context, creativity emerges as a driving force that not only empowers individuals to adapt and thrive but also propels societies forward. (Balci et al., 2023; Nazhifah et al., 2023). The ability to think innovatively, solve complex problems, and envision novel solutions is no longer a luxury but a necessity. Individuals are therefore confronted with a pressing need to cultivate and employ their creative potential in meeting current challenges where creativity has become synonymous with resilience, progress, and success.

In response to this pressing need, science education finds itself at a crucial juncture, ready to evolve and respond to the rapidly emerging challenges of our world. As breakthroughs in technology, shifts in the environment, and intricate societal issues redefine the boundaries of scientific exploration, fostering creativity within science education takes on heightened significance (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Oliveira et al., 2021). To empower the upcoming generation with the requisite skills to

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confront these challenges effectively, science education must wholeheartedly embrace and prioritize creativity as an essential component (Smare & Elfatih, 2023). This approach not only enables students to grasp the complexities of scientific principles but also equips them to employ their creative prowess in shaping a sustainable, innovative, and adaptable future.

Creativity is our capacity to find new solutions to the problems we encounter by using our existing knowledge. Creativity is being able to establish new correlations between concepts, and to present new experiences and ideas (products) around this axis of thought (Apaydin, 2023). In our age, where information is developing and changing very rapidly, societies need individuals who are proactive, thinking creative, problem-solving, and constantly improving themselves in order to adapt to this change and development (Smare & Elfatih 2023; Apaydin, 2023). Hence, it becomes evident that to secure sustainable development, there is a need for ongoing enhancement of the creative potential among individuals who shape society. This necessitates the implementation of innovative strategies that foster essential creativity skills, notably creative thinking.

Creative thinking refers to thinking that is trained by reviving imagination, paying attention to intuition, and revealing new things that need to be explored (Nazhifah et al., 2023; Aldossari, 2021). According to Ayua et al. (2023) Creative thinking is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. It is a positive action in stimulating brain function that can create a proper learning style. In whichever way one views creative thinking, it is generally considered as a process of thinking based on what has been or formed from the knowledge relationship with reality, which results in creating something new.

In the realm of science education, particularly at the basic education level, the cultivation of creative thinking skills hinges on a crucial factor: hands-on learning experiences facilitated by the use of teaching materials. Creative thinking in science goes beyond rote memorization of facts; it thrives when students are actively engaged in exploring, experimenting, and problem-solving (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Tanjung et al., 2023). By providing students with hands-on activities and tangible teaching materials, educators create a dynamic learning environment that encourages curiosity, critical thinking, and innovation. These activities not only enable students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts but also foster a deeper understanding of scientific concepts (Handayani et al., 2022). Moreover, they empower learners to ask questions, make connections, and develop a holistic appreciation for the scientific method, ultimately equipping them with the creative thinking skills necessary for both academic success and real-world problem-solving. However, research has consistently highlighted the scarcity of instructional materials in Nigerian basic schools (National Teachers' Institute - NTI as cited in Ikyernum et al., 2022). Often, the available materials are insufficient or outdated. This shortage poses a considerable challenge to teachers who aim to nurture creative thinking among their students. In this context, improvisation emerges as an essential strategy for Basic Science teachers, enabling them to adapt and create effective learning experiences using readily available materials.

Improvisation refers to selection or provision for something not readily available. It is the process by which educational materials can be designed and developed using locally available materials to meet specific instructional needs (Ayua et al., 2022; Ikyernum et al., 2022). Improvisation according to Ayua (2021) could be by substitution, modification and construction either solely by the teacher (Teacher Improvisation) or by the collaborative efforts of the teacher and learners (Collaborative Improvisation).

Teacher Improvisation (TI) refers to teaching aid(s) made by the teacher alone and brought to the classroom for Basic Science teaching. TI is an improvisation approach that is teacher-based because learners are not involved in the process of producing the improvised instructional material(s) (Ikyernum et al., 2022). Collaborative Improvisation (CI) on the other hand refers to teaching aids that are produced by the combined efforts of the teacher and the learners for the purpose of Basic Science teaching and learning (Ikyernum et al., 2022). This approach emphasizes the active involvement of both the teacher and the students in creating these materials. Through the implementation of a collaborative improvisation approach, students not only acquire vital subject knowledge but are also prompted to exercise their creative thinking skills well before formal lessons commence. This approach cultivates a highly engaging and interactive learning atmosphere, which is a sine-qua-none for engendering creative thinking skills in Basic Science learners. This study will centre its attention on these two improvisation techniques with the objective of evaluating their influence on creative-thinking fluency among upper Basic Science learners of diverse abilities.

Creative thinking plays a pivotal role in the improvisation of instructional materials, making them a necessity in the educational realm. When teachers and learners possess the ability to think creatively, they can adapt and transform existing materials, or even develop entirely new resources (Ikyernum et al., 2022). This flexibility not only ensures that the teaching materials align with the specific learning objectives and student demographics but also makes the learning experience more engaging and effective. Harnessing improvisation in the teaching and learning process has been recognized as a pathway to foster and enhance creative thinking in learners (Ayua et al., 2023). By nurturing creative thinking through improvisation,

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students not only acquire valuable competencies to thrive in society but also contribute to economic growth and progress in this technology-driven 21st-century economy. As a result, promoting creative thinking and improvisation in educational settings becomes essential for preparing learners to succeed in the ever-evolving world and its demands. Creative thinking comprises five sub domains of fluency, originality, elaboration, resistance to premature closure and abstractness of titles (Teheмба et al., 2023). However, this paper focuses on creative-thinking fluency.

Creative-thinking fluency is the ability to generate many ideas that come from one's mind quickly in response to open-ended questions or refers to a person's thinking process (Trisnayanti et al., 2020; Ayua et al., 2023). In creative-thinking fluency, the emphasis is on quantity, not quality (Handayani et al., 2022;). According to Torrance, creative-thinking fluency is the ability to generate several ideas or produce many answers. Fluency in creative thinking is of paramount importance in nurturing creativity. It signifies the ability to generate a multitude of novel ideas, solutions, or perspectives in a given context. Creative thinking fluency not only fosters innovation but also enhances problem-solving skills and encourages adaptability (Haruna, 2016). When individuals can effortlessly produce diverse and imaginative ideas, they are better equipped to tackle complex challenges, explore unconventional possibilities, and contribute meaningfully to their respective fields. Empirically, Handayani et al., (2022) in their study “Students’ creative thinking skills in Biology learning: Fluency, Flexibility, Originality, and Elaboration” established that students’ creative-thinking fluency was low. However, Balci et al., (2023) and Chua et al., (2020) in their respective studies on creative thinking established that learners gained higher creative thinking fluency as a result of creativity enhancement programs. Though the studies assessed the creative-thinking fluency of learners, they however were not concerned with creative-thinking fluency as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation across mixed ability learners as proposed by this study.

Mixed ability in this research refers to the different educational performance levels of students in Basic Science, which can be categorized as high, average, or low based on their past academic scores. Maikano (as cited in Ikyernum, et al., 2022) suggests that ability grouping is determined by educators' assessments of students' abilities. When assigning students to different tracks, their prior test scores or performance measures from previous grades or schools are considered to determine their ability levels. Students’ ability levels for the study were guided by Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2021) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2019) grading system for basic schools. Based on the grading system, High Ability Level (A = 75-100% and B = 65-74%), Average Ability Level (C = 55-64% and D = 45-54%) and Low Ability Level (E = 40-44% and F = 0-39%). By using this grading system, the researchers were able to distinguish and group students based on their academic ability levels in Basic Science. Empirically, Ikyernum et al., (2022) in their study “Effect of teacher-learner improvised material on creative thinking among mixed ability upper Basic Science students in Makurdi metropolis” established that the level of creative thinking among mixed ability students was significantly enhanced without gender disparity as a result of learners’ active involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials. However, Setiawan and Fitriani (2023) in their study “Analysis of mathematical creative thinking ability on junior high school students in Bandung” reported low creative thinking fluency in learners of varied abilities. These studies however were not concerned with creative-thinking fluency in relation to improvisation and did not tell whether a difference existed in creative-thinking fluency based on gender as a result of learners’ involvement in improvisation of instructional materials.

Gender differences encompass the characteristics associated with being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Research by Danjuma (as cited in Ayua, 2021) indicates that these gender disparities have a worldwide impact, particularly in Africa, by hindering the equal participation of boys and girls in Science Education. Consequently, these gender-specific factors influence the teaching, learning, and creative thinking of students in Basic Science. Empirically, Ulger and Morsunbul (2017); Zhang et al., (2020), in their respective studies on differences in creative thinking found that a significant difference existed in creative thinking abilities between males and females in favour of females. However, Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ikyernum, et al., (2022) and Ayua et al., (2023) found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking fluency respectively. However, none of the studies were concerned with creative-thinking fluency as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation. That is why it was important to investigate the impact of collaborative improvisation on upper Basic science students’ creative-thinking fluency.

Since the dawn of the 21st century, the world has witnessed remarkable progress in scientific and knowledge domains, driven by factors like the knowledge revolution and rapid technological advancements. Simultaneously, the contemporary era necessitates a workforce equipped with robust creativity skills to navigate the ever-evolving global landscape. These developments have exerted a profound influence on the educational system and its components. To remain in sync with these dynamic shifts, educational decision-makers must realign their strategies accordingly. In this context, upper Basic Science

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students must cultivate creative-thinking abilities to excel in their academic and professional pursuits. Improvisation stands out as a promising method for nurturing creativity in learners, given its capacity to stimulate spontaneous thinking, imaginative problem-solving, adaptability, and unconventional approaches. However, there is a need to thoroughly explore the extent to which improvisation techniques can effectively enhance the creative-thinking fluency among upper Basic Science students. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of collaborative improvisation on creative-thinking fluency in Basic Science among upper Basic Science students in Makurdi, Benue State.

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study were:

1. To determine the mean creative-thinking fluency scores among students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those exposed to Teacher Improvisation in Makurdi, Benue State.
2. To find out the mean creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation in Makurdi, Benue State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation?
2. What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation.
2. There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group design was used for this study. After pre-test administration, the experimental group of an intact class of 1:24 was taught concept of work, energy and power with 5 lesson plans using demonstration method blended with collaborative improvised materials (wooden toy car and wooden electric fan) constructed through active involvement of learners together with the teacher using procedures outlined in the lesson plans; while the control group was taught the same concept using same method blended with teacher improvised materials. This treatment lasted for five weeks. Thereafter, the students in both groups were given post-test. Students mixed ability were based on previous term's performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). A multistage sample of 52 (22 male and 30 female) Upper-Basic II students in two schools drawn from the population of 1337 (680 males and 657 females) Upper Basic II students in all the 21 secondary schools (Teaching Service Board Makurdi, 2021) was used for the study. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section "A" collected students' biodata; while section 'B' had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with the opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students' creative-thinking fluency in Basic Science. TTCT-Figural B was validated and trial-tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using a two-way Analysis of covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, measurement based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation?

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Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Fluency Scores of Students Taught using Collaborative Improvisation and Teacher Improvisation.

Ability Level	N	Group	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain difference
			$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD		
High	12	TI	7.08	1.084	7.83	1.193	0.75	1.05
	10	CI	7.10	1.270	8.90	0.316	1.80	
Average	8	TI	7.13	1.126	8.13	0.991	1	0.43
	7	CI	7.43	1.397	8.86	0.378	1.43	
Low	8	TI	7.00	1.309	7.50	1.069	0.50	1.79
	7	CI	6.57	0.767	8.86	0.378	2.29	
Cluster		TI	7.07		7.82		0.75	1.09
		CI	7.04		8.88		1.84	

Table 1 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores among mixed ability between experimental and control group with cluster means of 7.04 and 7.07. The table also shows that all the creative-thinking fluency mean scores among mixed ability in the experimental group were higher than those in the control group with cluster mean gain difference of 1.09

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Creative-Thinking Fluency Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Collaborative Improvisation (CI)

Ability Level	Gender	N	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
			$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD		
High	Male	7	7.09	1.375	8.45	1.035	1.36	0.27
	Female	3	7.09	1.044	8.18	1.079	1.09	
Average	Male	2	7.14	1.215	8.14	1.069	1.00	0.83
	Female	5	7.38	1.302	8.75	0.463	1.37	
Low	Male	2	7.25	1.258	7.75	1.258	0.5	1.13
	Female	5	6.64	1.027	8.27	1.009	1.63	
Cluster	Male		7.14		8.18		1.04	0.33
	Female		7.00		8.37		1.37	

Table 2 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores between male and female in the experimental group with cluster means of 7.14 and 7.00. Likewise, the table also shows that the creative-thinking fluency mean scores in the post-test was higher than those in the pre-test in both male and female with cluster mean gains of 1.04 and 1.37 respectively

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation and those taught using Teacher Improvisation.

Table 3: Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Fluency Test Scores of Students Based on Improvisation Technique

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	20.899 ^a	6	3.483	5.562	.000	.426
Intercept	53.237	1	53.237	85.018	.000	.654
Pre_TTCT	4.978	1	4.978	7.949	.007	.150
Improvisation-Technique	14.110	1	14.110	22.534	.000	.334
Ability_Level	.232	2	.116	.186	.831	.008

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Improvisation_Technique *	1.254	2	.627	1.001	.375	.043
Ability_Level						
Error	28.178	45	.626			
Total	3638.000	52				
Corrected Total	49.077	51				

a. R Squared = .426 (Adjusted R Squared = .349)

Table 3 shows no significant difference in the creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability students taught Basic Science using CI and those taught using TI, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.001$; $p = .375 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. However, the result also showed that students' creative-thinking fluency scores in the experimental group was better than those in the control group, $F_{(1, 45)} = 22.534$; $p = .000 < .05$. This implies that, although Collaborative Improvisation (CI) enhances creative-thinking fluency, it is not dependent on students' academic abilities

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency scores among mixed ability male and female students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation

Table 4. Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Fluency Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Using Collaborative Improvisation

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7.976 ^a	6	1.329	1.455	.215	.163
Intercept	51.923	1	51.923	56.848	.000	.558
Pre_TTCT	4.551	1	4.551	4.983	.031	.100
Gender	1.156	1	1.156	1.266	.266	.027
Ability_Level	.867	2	.434	.475	.625	.021
Gender * Ability_Level	2.358	2	1.179	1.291	.285	.054
Error	41.101	45	.913			
Total	3638.000	52				
Corrected Total	49.077	51				

a. R Squared = .163 (Adjusted R Squared = .051)

Table 4 showed no significant difference in the creative-thinking fluency scores between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.291$; $p = .285 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Collaborative Improvisation is gender unbiased; hence it enhanced creative-thinking fluency in both male and female mixed ability Basic Science students

Discussion of Findings

In regards to creative-thinking fluency based on involving them in improvising instructional materials, it was found that significant difference existed in creative- thinking fluency between students in the control and experimental groups in favour of those in the experimental group. However, among the ability levels there existed no significant difference in creative-thinking fluency. Following field experience, the finding of this study is not odd because during the construction process, students were given ample opportunity to fully express their open-mindedness towards generation of as many ideas that they can and as quick as possible which thus sharpened their overall thinking process. This finding is similar with those of Balci et al., (2023) and Chua et al., (2020) who found that there was a significant increase in creative-thinking fluency after students were exposed to creative thinking enhancement programs. However, the finding does not only contrast with, but is a potential solution to that of Handayani et al. (2022) who found that leaners' creative thinking fluency was low. The indifference among mixed ability students in creative-thinking fluency as found out, is similar to the finding of Ikyernum et al (2022) of no significant difference in creative thinking among varied ability students as they were actively involved in improvisation of instructional materials. However, the finding does not only differ with, but is also a potential solution to the finding of Setiawan and Fitriani (2023) who found low creative thinking fluency in learners of varied ability.

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Concerning students' creative-thinking fluency based on gender, it was discovered that no significant difference existed in creative-thinking fluency between male and female mixed ability students taught Basic Science using Collaborative Improvisation. Thus, involving students in the improvisation of instructional materials enhances their creative thinking fluency without difference in gender. This finding is similar to those of Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ikyernum et al., (2022) and Terhemba et al., (2023) who found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking fluency respectively. This finding however does not only differ, but also is solution to Ulger and Morsunbul (2017), Zhang et al., (2020) who found out that a significant difference existed between females and males upon creative thinking in favour of females.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-thinking fluency among mixed ability students can be enhanced without gender discrepancy if learners are actively involved in the improvisation of instructional materials.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to effectively implement this approach:

1. Collaborative Improvisation approach should be adopted in teaching Basic Science.
2. School administrators should encourage researchers to organize workshops on the use of Collaborative Improvisation.
3. Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers on Collaborative Improvisation.
4. School proprietors, heads and parents' teachers' association should materially/financially support Collaborative Improvisation in Basic Science.

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